

Characterization of Voltage Transformers for MV Applications up to 150 kHz - A Preliminary Study

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Abstract—The advance in the technology of semiconductors has led to the realization of power converters with increased switching frequency. Some technologies available for power converters allow, in addition, their direct connection to the Medium Voltage (MV) grids. This implies the widespread diffusion of high-frequency components, that are harmonics of the components around the switching frequency, also at the MV level. A reliable operation of the MV grids can be guaranteed only if these disturbances are correctly measured. Therefore, increased performance, in terms of accuracy in a wider frequency range, is requested to Instrument Transformers. In this paper, a measurement setup for the characterization of Voltage Transformers (VTs) in the frequency range from power frequency (50/60 Hz) up to 150 kHz is proposed. Some preliminary experimental results related to the characterization of two commercial VTs are also discussed.

Keywords—Instrument Transformer, Voltage Transformer, Power System Measurement, High-Frequency Components, Switching Power Converter

I. INTRODUCTION

Society's increasing use of switching devices (inverters, bulky power electronic converters, active filters, etc.), both as loads and as part of generators, especially for renewable energy sources, has driven a consequent proliferation of conducted disturbances on grid voltage and current, also at Medium voltage (MV) level, up to hundreds of kilohertz, due to the harmonics of the switching frequency.

For instance, the conducted emissions of new switching devices can interfere with Power Line Communication (PLC). PLC is a widely used communication technique over electrical grids to fulfil vital operations such as control and automation [1]; this interference degrades the quality of the delivered information and possible failures of vital grid operations can occur [2]-[4]. High-frequency emissions from one device

(both a load or a generator, including high-power converters) can easily couple with other devices, causing interference to the control system of the other devices, with possible consequent malfunctions or even complete failure. Moreover, these emissions increase the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the current that along with a pronounced skin effect, causes temperature increase and, consequently, accelerated aging and reduced useful life of components.

Recently, power converters, e.g. DC/DC (Direct Current), AC/DC (Alternating Current), and AC/AC, which make use of new generation switching components, e.g., Silicon Carbide (SiC) Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistors (MOSFET) [5], [6], allowing for increased switching frequencies, can be directly connected to MV power systems. This fact opens, also for MV grids, measurement needs that Low Voltage (LV) grids already experienced [7]-[10]. These needs, in turn, ask for new and improved performance, in terms of accuracy and wide frequency range. Unavoidably, the same requirements apply to Instrument Transformers (ITs), as they are the first element of every voltage and current measuring chain, in almost all applications.

From the point of view of standardization about ITs, the in-force standards that indicate the accuracy of ITs over power frequency (i.e. 50/60 Hz) are the IEC 61869 part 6 [11], 14 [12], and 15 [13]. They are focused on LPITs for MV and High Voltage (HV) grids and give accuracy requirements at power frequency but also at frequencies up to 20 kHz. However, they do not give indications on measurement methods, test procedures, possible reference instrumentation, or uncertainty evaluation at frequencies above power frequency. In this way it leaves to the manufacturer, or to the calibration laboratory, a complete arbitrariness on how to evaluate the fulfillment of the prescribed accuracy

requirement above power frequency, leaving, in turn, the final user in the impossibility to validate the performance of products.

The activity presented here is developed according to the framework of the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 “ADMIT” [14], which aims to establish suitable parameters for the definition of the accuracy of Voltage and Current Transformers (VTs and CTs), and the related measurement instrumentation, in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. A non-exhaustive list of the activities that will be carried out within this project is: definition of realistic waveforms, accuracy parameters and related procedures for the performance evaluation of ITs up to 150 kHz, development of new systems for the generation of AC (50/60 Hz) or DC voltages (up to 36 kV) and currents (up to 2 kA) with spectral components of reduced amplitudes up to 150 kHz, development of reference MV voltage and current sensors up to 150 kHz, contribution to the development of new standards about accuracy evaluation of MV ITs up to 150 kHz, within the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Technical Committee (TC) 38 “Instrument Transformers”.

As a starting point, this paper deals with the design and implementation of a measurement setup that allows for characterizing VTs up to 3.5 kV, in a frequency range from a few hertz up to 150 kHz.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II describes the implementation of the proposed measurement setup. Section III presents some preliminary results related to the characterization of two commercial MV VTs, one of which is inductive and the other is a Low Power Voltage Transformer (LPVT). Finally, Section IV draws the conclusions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A quite wide literature about the measurement of the frequency behaviour of VTs and CTs beyond the power frequency exists. For the sake of brevity, here only some papers are cited [15]-[20]. In the scientific community, it is quite widely recognized that the measurement of the frequency behaviour of the ITs should be performed by applying waveforms composed of a fundamental component (DC or AC 50/60 Hz) and other spectral components with reduced amplitude. However, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, in all the studies the involved frequency range is limited to 10 kHz. Most probably, the main reason for that is technological, linked to the fact that no ready solutions nor custom implementations are available on the market for the generation and measurement of this kind of waveforms with frequency content over some tens of kilohertz.

Another field of application that has some common points with the research topic of this paper is related to the measurement of high-voltage pulses [21]. The common points regard essentially the voltage range (up to tens of kilovolts, or even more) and the frequency range (from DC up to hundreds of kilohertz or more). However, there are critical differences between these two topics that make the methodologies of high voltage pulse measurement not directly applicable to the characterization of ITs, intended for power system applications, up to 150 kHz. The main reason is the great difference between the waveforms involved in these two applications. In the case of high voltage pulse measurement, they are simply short square or exponential pulses (in the order of $0.1 \div 10$ microseconds), whereas in the second case, they

Fig. 1. Basic block diagram of the proposed measurement setup

are composed of a fundamental tone (at DC or 50/60 Hz) and other high-frequency spectral components.

III. MEASUREMENT SETUP

A. Setup architecture

To the best of the authors’ knowledge, from the point of view of the measurement setup, the characterization of an MV VT or CT, in the frequency range from power frequency up to 150 kHz, is still an open issue. No National Metrology Institute (NMI) around the world is able, at least with a declared uncertainty, to do that.

For what concerns voltage, MV amplifiers that allow the simultaneous generation of the fundamental component (DC or AC 50/60 Hz) up to tens of kilovolts and high-frequency components, with reduced amplitude, are available on the market. However, their frequency range is limited up to 20 kHz [15], [16].

The solution here proposed consists of the separate generation of the Power Frequency Component (at 50/60 Hz) from the High-Frequency Components (HFCs). This can be done by using two different generators and by combining their outputs. The basic block diagram of the proposed solution is shown in Fig. 1. It proposes a classical characterization method based on the comparison [15]-[19] of the outputs of a reference VT and of a VT under test, by means of a comparator. Both the comparator as well as the reference VT should have sufficient accuracy in the frequency range from the power frequency up to 150 kHz.

From the point of view of generation, the basic block diagram in Fig. 1 can be implemented in different ways, depending on the used generators. For instance, if one of the two used generators presents a galvanic insulated output, the two generators can be connected in series to realize the sum of their outputs [20]. Instead, if neither of the two has a galvanic insulated output, a parallel connection can be adopted, provided that suitable filters are used to prevent damage to both generators.

Fig. 2. Detailed block scheme of the proposed measurement setup

For the case at hand, the Power Frequency Generator (PFG) is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), cascaded by a low-voltage amplifier, cascaded, in turns, by a step-up transformer to reach the required voltage levels. Instead, the high-frequency generator is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), cascaded by another low-voltage amplifier, having an output frequency range from DC up to 150 kHz. The proposed measurement setup is shown in Fig. 2.

As it can be seen from Fig. 2, the sum of the PFC and of the HFC is simply obtained by the series connection of the output of the Step-Up Transformer (SUT) and of the High-Frequency Amplifier (HFA). In particular, one terminal of the HFA is connected to the earth, and the other is connected to the lower potential terminal of the SUT. This is possible thanks to the intrinsic galvanic insulated output of the SUT.

B. Setup implementation

The reference voltage signal to be applied to the VT under test is provided by two arbitrary waveform generators (AWGs) National Instruments (NI) PCI eXtension for Instrumentation (PXI) 5422 (16 bit, variable output gain, ± 12 V output range, 200 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 256 MB of onboard memory). The comparator is realized by using a multifunction I/O module PXIe-6124 (± 10 V, 16 bit, and maximum sampling rate 4 MHz), that acquires the primary and secondary waveforms of the VT under test. The AWGs use an 8 MHz clock to generate the waveforms and this clock is used to derive the sampling clock, chosen as 4 MHz; this allows obtaining coherent sampling, thus avoiding spectral leakage.

The output of the first AWG (AWG 1) is connected to an arbitrary four-quadrant voltage and current amplifier Bolab (± 75 V, ± 20 A, 1 kW, DC – 1 MHz) feeding the VT under test through a 100 V / 24 kV SUT. The output of the second AWG (AWG 2) is connected to a high-speed bipolar amplifier NF (± 150 V, 200 VA, DC – 500 kHz). Primary voltages are scaled with a commercial high-voltage probe (HVP), that is the “Reference VT” in Fig. 2, having a scale factor of 1000:1 and uncertainties on ratio error of 15 mV/V (level of confidence 95%) from DC up to 5 MHz. A low-voltage divider (LVD), having a ratio of about 18.5 V/V and uncertainties on ratio errors of 10 mV/V (level of confidence 95%) from DC up to 150 kHz, has been designed and built for the measurement of the secondary voltage of the VT.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section provides preliminary results related to the generation of test waveforms and to the characterization of two commercial voltage transformers using the measurement setup described in Section III. The first VT is inductive, while the second one is an LPVT, based on capacitive sensing technology. The main specifications of the tested VTs are shown in Table I.

The generated test waveforms are composed of: 1) the fundamental component at 50 Hz; 2) one harmonic component. The amplitude of the fundamental component is chosen equal to 3 kV.

The frequency of the harmonic component varies from 1 kHz to 150 kHz, while its amplitude is chosen as equal to 3 % of fundamental tone. At each frequency involved in the characterization, the ratio error is measured as in (1),

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{k_r \cdot V_s(f) - V_p(f)}{V_p(f)}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- $k_r = V_{p,r} / V_{s,r}$ is the rated transformation ratio ($V_{p,r}$ and $V_{s,r}$ are the rated primary and secondary voltages);
- $V_p(f)$ and $V_s(f)$ are the RMS values of the primary and secondary harmonic voltages at frequency f .

TABLE I. RATED SPECIFICATION OF THE ANALYZED VTs

Type	Accuracy Class	Rated Primary Voltage (kV)	Rated Secondary Voltage (V)	Rated Burden (VA)
LPVT	0.5	$20/\sqrt{3}$	1	-
Inductive VT	0.5	3	100	25

Fig. 3. Ratio error of the tested LPVT

Fig. 4. Ratio error of the tested inductive VT

Fig. 3 shows the frequency behaviour of $\varepsilon(f)$ from 1 kHz to 150 kHz for the inductive VT under test. It can be observed that the first resonance of the VT occurs at about 12 kHz whereas the second, which involves a wider variation of the ratio error, is located between 110 kHz and 130 kHz.

It can also be seen that the ratio error keeps lower than 10 % up to about 60 kHz.

Fig. 4 shows the frequency behaviour of $\varepsilon(f)$ from 1 kHz to 150 kHz for the LPVT under test. First of all, it can be noted that a slight resonance occurs at about 50 kHz.

Secondly, the value of $\varepsilon(f)$ at 82 kHz is noticeably out of trend.

This is due to the presence of a disturbance in the output of the LPVT, introduced by the switching power supply necessary for its proper operation. It can also be seen that the ratio error keeps lower than 10 % up to about 50 kHz, whereas it is lower than 13 % up to 150 kHz, excluding the range around 82 kHz.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a preliminary study about the implementation of a measurement setup for the characterization of Voltage Transformers, for Medium Voltage grids, in the frequency range from power frequency (50/60 Hz) up to 150 kHz. It is based on the separate generation of the fundamental tone and the high-frequency components. The test waveform is obtained by the series connection of the outputs of the step-up transformer and of the high-frequency amplifier. Preliminary experimental results related to the characterization of two commercial VTs, one inductive and one LPVT, are also discussed.

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